

Synthesis of Fused Ring Systems. Part I.* Derivatives of 1,2,3,4,6,7,8,8a-Octahydronaphthoic Acid

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A study of the Robinson annelation reaction with dimethyl 1,4-dimethyl-3-oxocyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate (IIIa) to provide 1,2,3,4,6,7,8,8a-octahydronaphthoic acid derivative (IIa) has been made. The compound (IIa) has been converted into methyl 1,4-dimethyl-3-methoxyacarbonylmethyl-2-(β -methoxyacarbonyl-ethyl)cyclohexane-1-carboxylate (Ic). A new approach to alkyl 2-aryl-5-oxohexanoates (VIII) through the use of ethyl 2-arylacrylates (VI) is described. The Mannich-Robinson reactions for the synthesis of 4-aryl derivatives of type (II) have been investigated.

For the synthesis of 4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-3-carboxymethyl-2-(β -carboxyethyl)-1-methylcyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid (Ia) and similar compounds, which are desired as intermediates in the steroid type synthesis, 4-substituted 1-methyl-6-oxo-1,2,3,4,6,7,8,9a-octahydronaphthoic acid derivatives (II) are considered as promising starting materials. Model experiments were undertaken for building up the bicyclic system (II). It was considered that a simple octalin derivative, such as (IIa), would be ideal for the purpose of study.

(Ia): R = *p*-MeO.C₆H₄; R' = H.

(Ib): R = Me; R' = H.

(Ic): R = R' = Me.

(IIa): R = Me.

(IIb): R = Ph.

(IIc): R = *p*-MeO.C₆H₄.

Dimethyl 1,4-dimethyl-3-oxocyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate¹ (IIIa) was allowed to react with the methiodide of 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one in presence of potassium *t*-butoxide² to furnish a viscous material in 47% yield. The latter on short treatment with methanolic potassium hydroxide, followed by acidification, yielded a non-crystalline acidic material which was esterified with diazomethane to afford methyl 1,4-dimethyl-6-oxo-

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1. Dutta and Biswas, this *Journal*, 1961, **38**, 385.

2a. De Fau *et al.*, *J. Chem Soc.*, 1937, 53.

2b. Wilds and Shunk, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1943, **65**, 460; 1949, **71**, 3946.

1,2,3,4,6,7,8,8a-octahydronaphthoate (IIa) in 22% yield. It was characterised through a semicarbazone and U.V. absorption spectra.

(III)

(IV)

(V)

- (a): R = R'' = Me; R' = COOMe.
 (b): R = R'' = Me; R' = CHO.
 (c): R = R'' = Me; R' = H.
 (d): R = Ph; R' = COOMe; R'' = Me.
 (e): R = *p*-MeO.C₆H₄; R' = COOMe; R'' = Me.
 (f): R = Ph; R' = CH₂CH₂COMe; R'' = Me.
 (g): R = *p*-MeO.C₆H₄; R' = H; R'' = Me.
 (h): R = *p*-MeO.C₆H₄; R' = R'' = H.

When the above Mannich-Robinson reaction was carried out at room temperature, the product on chromatography provided a crystalline material, m.p. 162-63.5°, which showed no U.V. absorption for α β -unsaturated ketone. From analytical data, I.R., and N.M.R. spectra it has been assigned structure (IV)³.

When the formyl derivative (IIIb)^{2b} was employed in the Mannich-Robinson reaction instead of the β -keto-ester (IIa), no improvement in the yield of the unsaturated keto-ester (IIa) was observed, but it had the advantage that the starting material could be removed through alkali extraction.

Since (IIa) was formed under conditions, which would effect the equilibration of the groups to their stable conformation, the structural assignment of the bicyclic compound having COOMe (1), Me (4), and -CH₂-CH₂- (2) in the equatorial conformation with respect to the cyclohexane ring A of (IIa) would not be unreasonable.

The keto-ester (IIa) was catalytically hydrogenated, using 10% palladised charcoal. Assuming that the hydrogenation proceeds through addition of hydrogen from the least hindered side of the molecule⁴, the hydrogenated product is represented by (V). The reduced ester (V) was treated with ethyl formate in presence of sodium methoxide. The formyl derivative of the keto-ester (V) was treated with hydroxylamine hydrochloride in acetic acid at 70-80°, according to the procedure of Johnson and Shelberg⁵, to yield the isoxazole. The isoxazole was directly boiled with 30% alkali on acidification an acidic material⁶ which could not be crystallised. This was purified through esterification, when

3. Alternative structures, see Johnson *et al.*, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1960, 82, 614.

4. Linstead *et al.*, *ibid.*, 1942, 64, 1985.

5. *Ibid.*, 1945, 67, 1754.

⁶2-Hydroxymethylencyclohexanone, when subjected to the same series of reactions, was found to provide pimelic acid in 31% yield.

the tri-ester (Ic) (possibly having carboxyl and propionic acid chain *cis*) was obtained as a viscous oil.

Our attention was next directed to the more complex derivatives, e.g., methyl 1-methyl-4-phenyl-6-oxo-1,2,3,4,6,7,8,8a-octahydronaphthoate (IIb) and methyl 1-methyl-4-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)-6-oxo-1,2,3,4,6,7,8,8a-octahydronaphthoate (IIc). The corresponding β -keto-esters (III d and III e) were accessible through syntheses similar to those described by Banerjee⁶ and by Bardhan⁷.

In the present investigation the procedure of Banerjee⁶ was followed with the modification that the intermediate 2-aryl-5-oxohexanoic acid derivative (VIII) was obtained through Michael addition of ethyl acetoacetate to ethyl 2-phenylacrylate (VIa) or to ethyl 2-(*p*-methoxyphenyl)acrylate (VIb) and acid hydrolysis of the resulting β -keto-ester (VII), followed by esterification.

(VIa): R = H.

(VIb): R = OMe.

(VIIa): R = H; R' = COOEt; R'' = Et.

(VIIb): R = OMe; R' = COOEt; R'' = Et.

(VIIIa): R = R' = H; R'' = Et.

(VIIIb): R = OMe; R' = H; R'' = Me.

The β -keto-ester (III d) was allowed to react with the methiodide of 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one in presence of potassium butoxide⁴ and the product was successively treated with acid and alkali, followed by esterification of the acidic material. The ester, thus obtained, did not show U. V. absorption, characteristic of $\alpha\beta$ -unsaturated ketone, and hence it was assigned the uncyclised structure (IIIf).

With a view to studying the course of the Mannich-Robinson reaction on the β -keto-ester (III e), it was treated with the methiodide of 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one in presence of potassium butoxide⁴ to furnish a product from which the unchanged β -keto-ester was removed chromatographically. The product, thus obtained, was successively treated with acid and alkali, followed by esterification with diazomethane, to afford the methyl ester (IIc) in 3% yield. It furnished a dark red oil on interreaction with 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazine. The keto-ester (IIc) did not solidify when seeded with the keto-ester (III g) which was obtained as a colorless crystalline solid, m.p. 107-108°, by esterification of the corresponding keto-acid (III h), m.p. 152-53°. Further work is in progress.

*EXPERIMENTAL

Methyl 1,4-Dimethyl-6-oxo-1,2,3,4,6,7,8,8a-octahydronaphthoate (IIa).—To an ice-cold, stirred mixture of methiodide of 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one (3.8 g.) and a solu-

6. *Science & Culture*, 1940, 5, 565, 715.

7. *Chem. & Ind.*, 1940, 369; *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1940, 848.

*All m.p.s are uncorrected. The U. V. absorption spectra were taken in 95% ethanol by a Beckman DU spectrophotograph, G 2400.

tion of dimethyl 1,4-dimethyl-3-oxocyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate[†] (IIIa) (6 g.) in butanol[†] (12 ml) and thiophene-free benzene (7.5 ml) was added dropwise, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, a solution of potassium butoxide[†] (K, 1.2 g.; BuOH[†], 30 ml). When the addition was complete, stirring was continued for 4 hours and the mixture left at room temperature for 14 hours. After refluxing for 3 hours, the solvents were evaporated at the water pump. The yellowish residue was acidified with dilute acetic acid and extracted with a mixture of ether and benzene. The extract was washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Distillation gave after removal of the lower boiling fractions a viscous liquid (3.7 g., 47%), b.p. 160-75°/0.2 mm. This fraction (3.6 g.) was refluxed with 10% KOH solution (150 ml) for 3 hours in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The mixture was cooled, acidified with HCl (dil.), and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). After removal of the ether, the crude acid was esterified (diazomethane). Working up in the usual way and distillation provided the *keto-ester* (IIa) (0.6 g., 22%), b.p. 135-50°/0.4 mm; λ_{max} 238 mμ (log ε, 4.2). (Found: C, 70.98; H, 8.72. C₁₄H₂₀O₃ requires C, 71.15; H, 8.53%).

The *semicarbazone* was crystallised from methanol, m.p. 235° (decomp.). (Found: C, 61.12; H, 8.05. C₁₅H₂₃O₃N₃ requires C, 61.44; H, 7.87%).

Dimethyl 2-(γ-Ketobutyl)-1,4-dimethyl-3-oxocyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate (IV).—The Mannich-Robinson reaction was carried out with the β-keto-ester[†] (IIIa) (7 g.), the methiodide of 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one (4.5 g.), and potassium butoxide[†] (K, 1.2 g.; BuOH[†], 30 ml) as before. The mixture was left at room temperature for 16 hours. The solvent was slowly distilled at the water pump during ¼ hr., the volume being maintained by slow addition of benzene. The mixture was cooled, diluted with water, and acidified with acetic acid. The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined organic layers were washed with water and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvents left a residue (8 g.) which was chromatographed on alumina (240 g.). On successive elution with petroleum (b.p. 67-70°), a mixture of petroleum (b.p. 67-70°) and benzene (1:1), and finally benzene, no product could be isolated. Recovery of the organic material by elution with ethanol and distillation of ethanol afforded a solid residue (1.62 g.) which was crystallised from 95% ethanol in colorless needles (1.15 g.), m.p. 162-63.5°. It did not show positive FeCl₃ reaction. The I.R. spectrum had bands at 1735 cm⁻¹ (strong) (ester carbonyl), 1715 cm⁻¹ (medium) (six-membered carbonyl), and 1230 cm⁻¹ (C-O stretching). The N.M.R. spectrum showed absorption at 8.89 p.p.m. (angular Me), 8.72 (CH₂-CH-CO), 8.69 (3), 8.17 and 8.01 (C-CH₂-C), 7.77 (-CH₂-CO), 7.2 (CH₂-C-CO), 6.32 and 6.27 (COOMe). (Found: C, 61.21; H, 8.02. C₁₆H₂₄O₆ requires C, 61.52; H, 7.74%).

Mannich-Robinson Reaction of the Formyl Derivative (IIIb).—The Mannich-Robinson reaction was carried out with the crude formyl derivative (IIIb) (4.7 g.) (prepared from 5.5 g. of the keto-ester, IIIc), the methiodide of 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one (3.43 g.), and potassium butoxide[†] (K, 1 g.; BuOH[†], 25 ml) as before. The mixture was refluxed for 3 hours and the solvent removed. The residue was diluted with water, acidified with cold HCl (dil.), and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with ice-cold 2% KOH solution[†] to remove the unchanged hydroxymethylene derivative, then with water till neutral, and dried (Na₂SO₄). Removal of the ether and distillation provided a viscous oil (2 g.), b.p. 155-65°/2 mm. Nitrogen was bubbled for 2½ hours through a solution of 1 g.-portion of

the oil in methanol (100 ml) containing KOH (4 g.), dissolved in water (8 ml). The mixture was poured into a saturated NaCl solution (300 ml) and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water, dried (Na_2SO_4), and concentrated. This residue along with the ester, obtained by esterification (CH_3N_2) of the fraction which underwent hydrolysis, was evaporatively distilled to yield an oil (0.35 g.); b.p. $95\text{--}105^\circ/1.5$ mm, λ_{max} 238 $m\mu$ ($\log \epsilon$, 4.17). Semicarbazone, m.p. 235° (decomp.).

Methyl 1,4-Dimethyl-3-oxocyclohexane-1-carboxylate (IIIc).—A mixture of 1,4-dimethyl-3-oxocyclohexane-1-carboxylic acid¹ (10 g.), methanol (50 ml), and H_2SO_4 (d 1.84, 3.5 ml) was refluxed for 60 hours. Working up and distillation afforded an oil (8 g.); b.p. $105\text{--}107^\circ/3$ mm (lit.⁶ b.p. $82\text{--}85^\circ/1$ mm). (Found: C, 65.01; H, 8.67. Calc. for $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$: C, 65.19; H, 8.75%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from methanol in orange needles, m.p. $178\text{--}79^\circ$ (lit.⁶ m.p. $180\text{--}81^\circ$). (Found; N, 15.12. Calc. for $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{20}\text{O}_6\text{N}_4$: N, 15.36%).

1-Methoxycarbonyl-1,4-dimethyldecal-6-one (V).—The unsaturated keto-ester (IIa) (1.6 g.) was hydrogenated, using 10% Pd-C catalyst (0.1 g.) in purified ethanol (20 ml). When the uptake of hydrogen was complete (6 hrs.), palladised charcoal was filtered. The filtrate, on removal of the ethanol, followed by evaporative distillation, furnished a colorless oil (1.2 g.), b.p. $90\text{--}95^\circ/0.4$ mm. (Found: C, 70.26; H, 9.37. $\text{C}_{14}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 70.54; H, 9.30%).

Methyl 1,4-Dimethyl-3-methoxycarbonylmethyl-2-(β -methoxycarbonylethyl)cyclohexane-1-carboxylate (Ic).—To an ice-cold suspension of sodium methoxide (Na, 0.3 g.; MeOH, 0.3 ml) in thiophene-free benzene (15 ml) was added dropwise, in an atmosphere of nitrogen, a solution of the keto-ester (V) (1.5 g.) and ethyl formate (2 ml) in benzene (10 ml) with stirring. After completion of the addition, the mixture was stirred for 2 hours and left at room temperature for 24 hours. After the usual working up and removal of the solvent, the hydroxymethylene derivative (1.2 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (10 ml) and on the addition of hydroxylamine hydrochloride (0.6 g.) the mixture was stirred for 2 hours at $70\text{--}80^\circ$. A solution of KOH (89 g.) in water (234 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 30 hours, when the evolution of ammonia ceased. The mixture was cooled, acidified with HCl, saturated with NaCl, and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with brine, dried (Na_2SO_4), and concentrated to a residue (0.5 g.) which could not be crystallised, but esterification (diazomethane), followed by evaporative distillation, furnished the trimethyl ester (Ic) (0.3 g.) as an oil, b.p. $115\text{--}20^\circ/0.2$ mm. (Found; C, 62.02; H, 8.67. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{26}\text{O}_8$ requires C, 62.17; H, 8.59%).

Pimelic Acid from 2-Hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone.—A mixture of 2-hydroxymethylenecyclohexanone⁹ (5.4 g.), hydroxylamine hydrochloride (3.65 g.), and acetic acid (30 ml) was stirred for 2 hours at $70\text{--}80^\circ$. A solution of KOH (171 g.) in water (450 ml) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 40 hours. The mixture was acidified with HCl and charcoaled. The filtrate was evaporated to dryness and the organic material taken in acetone. Removal of the acetone left a residue (2 g., 31%) which was crystallised from

8. Protiva *et al.*, *Coll. Czech. Chem. Comm.*, 1961, **26**, 730.

9. Plattner *et al.*, *Helv. Chim. Acta*, 1945, **28**, 771.

benzene in colorless crystals, m.p. 103-104°, which remained undepressed on admixture with an authentic specimen of pimelic acid.

Ethyl 4-Ethoxycarbonyl-5-keto-2-phenylhexanoate (VIIa).—To an ice-cold solution of sodium ethoxide (Na, 0.4 g., EtOH, 12.5 ml) was added dropwise ethylacetoacetate (22 ml) with shaking, followed by, after a period of $\frac{1}{2}$ hr., a solution of freshly distilled ethyl α -phenylacrylate¹⁰ (24.8 g.) in benzene (30 ml). The mixture was left overnight, refluxed for 5 hours, and set aside for 4 days. The mixture was acidified with acetic acid, diluted with water, and extracted with benzene. The extract was washed with water till free of the acid. Removal of the solvent provided a residue which was distilled to furnish the β -keto-ester (VIIa) (32.3 g., 75%) as an oil; b.p. 168-70°/2mm, n_D^{20} 1.4923. (Found: C, 66.38; H, 7.52. C₁₇H₂₂O₅ requires C, 66.63; H, 7.21%).

Ethyl 5-Keto-2-phenylhexanoate (VIIIa).—The β -keto-ester (VIIa) (32 g.) was refluxed with HCl (20%, 160 ml) for 16 hours. The mixture was cooled, saturated with NaCl, extracted with ether, and the extract dried (Na₂SO₄). The extract on being concentrated gave a residue (26 g.) which was refluxed for 18 hours with ethanol (60 ml) and H₂SO₄ (d 1.84: 3.6 ml), affording the keto-ester (VIIIa) (20.6 g., 84%) as an oil; b.p. 150-55°/3.5 mm (lit.⁶ b.p. 143-45°/4.5 mm; 160°/9 mm⁷), n_D^{20} 1.4954. (Found: C, 71.61; H, 7.82. Calc. for C₁₄H₁₈O₃: C, 71.76; H, 7.74%).

Trimethyl 2-Methyl-5-phenylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (IX).—Following the method of Banerjee⁶, the keto-ester (VIIIa) (20.2 g.) yielded 2-methyl-5-phenylpentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylic acid (26.7 g.) which was refluxed for 60 hours with methanol (165 ml) and H₂SO₄ (d 1.84, 22 ml). The usual working up and distillation produced the ester (IX) (21.8 g.) as an oil, b.p. 200-203°/2 mm (reported b.p. of the ethyl ester, 202-204°/5 mm⁶; 208°/7 mm⁷). (Found: C, 64.12; H, 7.27. C₁₈H₂₄O₆ requires C, 64.26; H, 7.19%).

Dimethyl 1-Methyl-3-oxo-4-phenylcyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate (IIId).—A mixture of the ester (IX) (21.8 g.), molecularised sodium (3 g.) in dry thiophene-free benzene (150 ml), and methanol (0.1 ml) was refluxed for 6 hours in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The mixture was cooled and acidified with ice-cold HCl (dil.). The benzene layer was separated and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The combined organic layers were washed with brine and dried (Na₂SO₄). Evaporation of the solvents and distillation of the residue yielded the β -keto-ester (IIId) (13 g., 66%) as an oil, b.p. 185-90°/1.5 mm. (Found: C, 67.12; H, 6.71. C₁₇H₂₀O₃ requires C, 67.07; H, 7.60%).

Methyl 2-(γ -Ketobutyl)-1-methyl-3-oxo-4-phenylcyclohexane-1-carboxylate (IIIIf).—The Mannich-Robinson reaction was carried out with the β -keto-ester (IIId) (12 g.), the methiodide of 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one (5.6 g.), and potassium butoxide⁴ (K, 1.85g.; BuOH⁴, 30 ml), as described before. Working up and concentration furnished a residue (17 g.) which was refluxed for 20 hours with acetic acid (255 ml) and HCl (30%, 85 ml) in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The volatile solvent was evaporated at the water pump; the residue was diluted with water and extracted with ether. Evaporation of the dried (Na₂SO₄) extract provided a residue which was refluxed for 60 hours with methanol (75 ml) and H₂SO₄ (d 1.84, 10.5 ml). The ester was worked up and distilled at 0.4 mm to yield fractions (i) 4 g., b.p. 168-73° and (ii) 4.7 g., b.p. 185-215°.

A mixture of fraction (ii) (2.3 g.) and 10% methanolic KOH solution (580 ml) was refluxed for 2 hours in an atmosphere of nitrogen. Methanol was evaporated at the water

pump. The residue was cooled, acidified with HCl and extracted with ether. The extract was washed with brine and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the ether yielded a residue which was esterified (diazomethane) to provide the *keto-ester* (III f) (1.25 g.) as an oil, b.p. 168-80°/0.3 mm. (Found: C, 71.99; H, 7.56. $\text{C}_{10}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_4$ requires C, 72.12; H, 7.64%). The analytical data remained almost constant even after treatment of the aforementioned *keto-ester* (III f) with 45% methanolic KOH, followed by esterification (CH_2N_2). The 2,4-DNP crystallised from ethyl acetate in orange needles, m.p. 158-59°. The investigation on fraction (i) was inconclusive. (Found: C, 69.24; H, 7.29%).

Ethyl α -(p-Methoxyphenyl)acrylate (VI b).—A mixture of *p*-methoxyphenylacetonitrile¹¹ (101 g.), ethanol (95%, 695 ml), and H_2SO_4 (conc., 73 ml) was gently refluxed for 30 hours. The mixture was cooled and poured into water (1.5 litres). The organic layer was separated, washed with 5% NaOH solution, followed by water till neutral, and distilled to afford ethyl *p*-methoxyphenylacetate (98 g., 74%) as an oil, b.p. 134-36°/5 mm (reported^{12,13} b.p., 136-37°/10 mm, 139-41°/7 mm).

To an ice-cold suspension of sodium ethoxide (Na, 9.5 g; EtOH, 25 ml) in anhydrous ether (150 ml) was added dropwise diethyl oxalate (62.5 g.), followed by ethyl *p*-methoxyphenylacetate (77 g.). On refluxing the mixture for 1 hour, a yellow solid was deposited which was left overnight. The sodio-salt was filtered, washed with ether, and decomposed with ice-cold HCl (dil.). The precipitated oil was taken up in ether and the aqueous layer extracted with ether. The extract was washed with water and dried (Na_2SO_4). Removal of the ether afforded a residue (107 g.) which was treated with formaldehyde (38%, 59 ml) and potassium carbonate solution (K_2CO_3 , 45 g.; water, 250 ml). After 20 mins. the reaction mixture was extracted with ether, the extract was washed with water till neutral, and dried (Na_2SO_4). Evaporation of the ether yielded a residue which was distilled to provide ethyl α -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)acrylate (VI b) (34.1 g., 41%) as a colorless oil, b.p. 132-36°/5 mm. (Found: C, 69.7; H, 7.02. $\text{C}_{12}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_3$ requires C, 69.88; H, 6.84%).

Ethyl 4-Ethoxycarbonyl-5-keto-2-(p-methoxyphenyl)hexanoate (VII b).—The Michael condensation was carried out with sodium ethoxide (Na, 0.6 g.; EtOH, 18.75 ml), ethyl acetate (33 ml), and ethyl α -(*p*-methoxyphenyl)acrylate (VI b) (34 g.) as before. Working up and concentration afforded a residue which was distilled to furnish the β -*keto-ester* (VII b) (36 g., 65%) as an oil; b.p. 200-205°/3 mm, n_D^{20} 1.4979. (Found: C, 64.62; H, 7.25. $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 64.27; H, 7.19%).

Methyl 5-Keto-2-(p-methoxyphenyl)hexanoate (VIII b).—The β -*keto-ester* (VII b) (36 g.) was refluxed with HCl (20%, 350 ml) for 20 hours. Working up as before and distillation of the ether provided a residue (26 g.) which was methylated with dimethyl sulphate (34.4 ml) and NaOH (2*N*, 200 ml) at 50-60°. The mixture was cooled, acidified with HCl and extracted with ether. Evaporation of the dried extract yielded a residue (23 g.) which was refluxed for 18 hours with methanol (50 ml) and H_2SO_4 (*d* 1.84, 3 ml), providing the *keto-ester* (VIII b) (19.1 g., 71%) as a pale yellow oil, b.p. 152-55°/0.4 mm (reported b.p.

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12. Livabita et al., *J. Gen. Chem., USSR.*, 1947, 17, 1671.

13. Dankova et al., *ibid.*, 1951, 21, 787.

of the ethyl ester 162-63°/2.3 mm⁶; 180°/8 mm⁷). (Found: C, 67.48; H, 7.28. C₁₄H₁₈O₄ requires C, 67.18; H, 7.24%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from methanol in orange needles, m.p. 122-23°. (Found: N, 12.94. C₂₀H₂₂O₇N₄ requires N, 13.02%).

The semicarbazone crystallised from methanol in needles, m.p. 152-53°. (Found: C, 58.74; H, 6.91. C₁₅H₂₁O₄N₃ requires C, 58.61; H, 6.89%).

Trimethyl 2-Methyl-5-(p-methoxyphenyl)pentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylate (X).—Following the procedure of Banerjee⁶, the keto-ester (VIIIb) (18 g.) afforded 2-methyl-5-(p-methoxyphenyl) pentane-1,2,5-tricarboxylic acid (20.5 g.) which was esterified with methanol (150 ml) and H₂SO₄ (d 1.84, 21 ml). The ester was distilled to furnish a viscous oil (17.5 g.), b.p. 204-205°/1 mm (reported b.p. of the ethyl ester, 220-25°/3.5 mm⁶; 228°/6mm⁷). (Found: C, 62.01; H, 7.27. C₁₉H₂₅O₇ requires C, 62.27; H, 7.15%).

Dimethyl 1-Methyl-3-oxo-4-(p-methoxyphenyl)cyclohexane-1,2-dicarboxylate (IIIe).—Dieckmann cyclisation of the ester (X) (17.5 g.) was carried out as before, using sodium (2.2 g.) and benzene (40 ml). Working up in the usual way and distillation afforded the β-keto-ester (IIIe) (8g., 50%), b.p. 200-212°/1.5 mm. (Found: C, 64.71; H, 6.69. C₁₈H₂₂O₆ requires C, 64.65; H, 6.63%).

1-Methyl-3-oxo-4-(p-methoxyphenyl)cyclohexane-1-carboxylic Acid (IIIh).—The β-keto-ester (IIIe) (7.5 g.) was refluxed with acetic acid (100 ml) and HCl (10%, 50 ml) for 20 hours in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The mixture was concentrated as before, diluted with water, and extracted with ether. On evaporation of the ether, the residue (15 g.) was methylated with dimethyl sulphate (25 ml) and NaOH (2N, 200 ml) at 50-60°. With the addition of NaOH (8 g.), dissolved in water (50 ml), the mixture was heated for 2 hours, cooled, acidified with HCl, and extracted successively with ether and chloroform. The combined extract was washed with brine (20 ml), dried (Na₂SO₄), and concentrated to a residue (7 g.) which was crystallised from a mixture of chloroform and ether in colorless needles, m.p. 152-53°. (Found: C, 68.53; H, 7.12. C₁₅H₁₈O₄ requires C, 68.68; H, 6.91%).

Methyl 1-Methyl-3-oxo-4-(p-methoxyphenyl)cyclohexane-1-carboxylate (IIIg).—The keto-acid (IIIh) (7 g.) was refluxed with methanol (100 ml) and H₂SO₄ (d 1.84, 10 ml) for 48 hours. Working up and distillation furnished the keto-ester (IIIg) (4 g.), b.p. 180-200°/0.3 mm. It was crystallised from chloroform-ether mixture (1:10; v/v), m.p. 107-108°. (Found: C, 69.43; H, 7.21. C₁₆H₂₀O₄ requires C, 69.54; H, 7.29%).

The 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazone crystallised from ethyl acetate in orange needles, m.p. 159-60°. (Found: C, 58.04; H, 5.36. C₂₂H₂₄O₇N₄ requires C, 57.88; H, 5.36%).

Methyl 1-Methyl-4-(p-methoxyphenyl) 6-cxo-1,2,3,4,6,7,8,8a-cctalydroxaphthate (IIc).—The Mannich-Robinson reaction was carried out with β-keto-ester (IIIe) (8 g.), methiodide of 1-diethylaminobutan-3-one (3.5 g.), and potassium butoxide⁴ (K, 1g.; BuOH⁵, 25 ml) as before. Working up and concentration yielded a residue (8.4 g.) which was chromatographed on alumina (240 g.), using benzene as eluent. On evaporation of the solvent, the eluted material (no ferric chloride colour) was evaporatively distilled to furnish a viscous oil (0.5 g.), b.p. 130-35°/0.3 mm. This was refluxed for 7 hours with acetic acid (15 ml) and HCl (30%, 7.5 ml) in an atmosphere of nitrogen. Working up as before afforded a

residue (0.6 g.) which was refluxed for 2 hours with KOH solution (20%, 25 ml) in an atmosphere of nitrogen. The mixture was cooled, acidified with iced HCl, and extracted with ether. Concentration of the dried extract provided a residue (0.35 g.) which was esterified with diazomethane and evaporatively distilled to furnish an oil (0.2 g., 3%), b.p. 125-35°/0.4 mm. (Found: C, 72.81; H, 7.28. $C_{26}H_{24}O_4$ requires C, 73.14; H, 7.36%).

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